

Yādiya/Sam'al

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The Kingdom of Yādiya, based at the city of Sam'al (modern Zincirli Höyük), was founded sometime in the 10th century BCE. Though the city's history stretches back to the Early Bronze Age, it was destroyed during the Late Bronze Age and remained unoccupied until it was resettled at the foundation of the kingdom. The kingdom's cultural practices are particularly notable for their combination of traditions otherwise known from so-called Aramean and Neo-Hittite polities. The kingdom also incorporated elements of Assyrian culture derived from interactions that began during the reign of Shalmaneser III in the mid-9th century. Later, the kingdom became a vassal of Tiglath-Pileser III in the late 8th century. At the end of the same century, the kingdom was abolished incorporated into the Assyrian empire as a province. Primary sources attest to a heterogeneous population in Yādiya. An early inscription describes two social groups (called mškbm and the b'rrm) in a conflict that was resolved through the efforts of the king. The distinction between these groups remains unknown. While there is evidence for speech communities utilizing Semitic (particularly Sam'alian) and Indo-European languages (particularly Luwian), there is no direct evidence for these groups acknowledging ethnic or other social divisions between them. The royal family of Yādiya, for instance, primarily composed royal inscriptions in Semitic languages and sometimes took Semitic names, but Luwian names were somewhat more common. The pantheon of Yādiya may have been vast, and a broken inscription from the site makes mention of "the thousand gods," making it the sole Iron Age polity known to have continued the Hittite tradition of referring to their pantheon in that way. More specifically, various kings are known to have been devoted to personal deities (such as King Gabbar's tutelary deity Ba'al-Šemed), but the dynastic god was Rakib-El. Based on comparative evidence from the surrounding region, this dynastic god may have been a storm-god. Other storm-gods were worshipped as well, however, chief among them Hadad whose primary cult place may have been Gerçin. The Katumuwa inscription further mentions a Hadad of the Vineyards and a Hadad the Host as though they are separate deities, but the precise relationship between them is unknown. The same is true for Resheph and Arq-Resheph. Apart from these, the Yādiyans revered a mix of deities known from other Levantine and Mesopotamian sources, including the sun-god Shamash, the moon-god of Haran, and Ba'al-Ḥammon as well as the goddesses Kubaba and Nikkurawas. It is theorized that Kubaba may have been the consort of Rakib-El, but this is not confirmed by the epigraphic evidence. The best understood of Yādiya's rituals were devoted to the royal family. These included but were not limited to mortuary feasts performed on a semi-regular basis. These were carried out in large ceremonial plazas on the acropolis, and in the royal necropolis at Gerçin. In the 8th century, such rituals were extended to non-royal elites as well and carried out in household contexts. Candidates for temples have not been extensively studied, so possible temple rituals remain mysterious.

Date Range: 920 BCE - 713 BCE

Region: Yādiya/Sam'al

Region tags: Asia Minor, Levant

The kingdom of Yādiya was based at the city of Sam'al (Zincirli Höyük), but it also included a necropolis at Gerçin and perhaps more of the surrounding area.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Struble, Eudora J., and Virginia Rimmer Herrmann. "An eternal feast at Sam'al: the new Iron Age mortuary stele from Zincirli in context." *Bulletin of the American Schools of Oriental Research* 356.1 (2009): 15-49.
- Source 2: Cornelius, Izak. "In Search of the Goddesses of Zincirli (Sam'al)." *Zeitschrift des Deutschen Palästina-Vereins* (2012): 15-25.
- Source 3: Sanders, Seth L. "The appetites of the dead: West Semitic linguistic and ritual aspects of the Katumuwa Stele." *Bulletin of the American Schools of Oriental Research* 369.1 (2013): 35-55.

Notes: This is a sample of publications that focus on religion in Yādiya/Sam'al. When the Chicago-Tübingen Expedition to Zincirli releases its excavation reports, these should contain the most up-to-date and detailed data pertinent to this topic

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.hittitemonuments.com/>
- Source 1 Description: This website contains brief descriptions along with high resolution photos and isometric reconstructions of many of the artifacts and architectural settings relevant to religious practice in Yādiya/Sam'al.
- Source 2 URL: <https://zincirli.uchicago.edu/>
- Source 2 Description: Official website of the Chicago-Tübingen Expedition to Zincirli.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7kAuaMMpMS4>
- Source 1 Description: This video presents a specific ritual artifact (the Katumuwa Stele) and reconstruction of its attached ritual, including a reading of the ritual text.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <http://web-corpora.net/LuwianCorpus/search/>
- Source 1 Description: This corpus includes the hieroglyphic Luwian inscriptions relevant to understanding Yādiya/Sam'al.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The denizens of Yādiya/Sam'al certainly came into contact with people who practiced different rituals and worshiped other deities, but it is not clear how such people would have been categorized with regard to in-group/out-group relations.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: Affiliation with the religious group most likely depended on living within the respective region rather than a recruitment process.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Based on current evidence, there is no clear differentiation between religious and secular spheres. The political system is a religious system.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 8000

Notes: The exact population is impossible to determine. This number is based on Zorn's suggestion of 200 persons per hectare in a walled Iron Age city state in a fertile setting. This does not account for the denizens of other sites connected to the polity, however. See Zorn, J. R. 1994. Estimating the population size of ancient settlements: methods, problems, solutions, and a case study. *Bulletin of the American Schools of Oriental Research* 295:31-48.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 100

Notes: Because the regional polity and the religious group are not clearly differentiated, presumably everyone within the polity had some connection to the religious group.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: Certain monumental inscriptions preserved authoritative ritual instructions (e.g. for mortuary practice targeted at specific individuals), but these artifacts were not necessarily experienced by the group as 'texts' nor were they accessible to the group at large. Thus, while this religious group does have a concept of authoritative/sacred writing, this concept was likely not coextensive with that of Scripture.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– No

Notes: Comparative evidence from the surrounding region may suggest that this group practiced cremation, but direct evidence for this has yet to be found. If this was the case, it may explain why tombs have not been discovered.

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Notes: Gercin appears to have been a royal necropolis. The Katumuwa Stele implies that other elites may have practiced funerary rites in their homes or another such local space, but these include no evidence for burial.

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: Some comparative and circumstantial evidence suggests that altars were used by the group.

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: Inscribed amulets and iconographic amulets that represent miniaturizations of significant cult scenes have been found.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated

using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Palaces

Notes: Sam'al's acropolis contained numerous palaces which served religious purposes as part of their political function.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):
 - Field doesn't know
- Notes: Much of the symbolism from the site is still poorly understood.

- ↳ Humans:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other features of iconography:
 - Yes
- Notes: One of the most significant features of iconography in this region is the depiction of ritual practice. The iconography includes depictions of feasts (including food and necessary utensils) as well as ritual processions. Vegetal imagery is also important.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Multiple texts refer to some form of personhood (probably an individual's social/ritual agency) that could be operative apart from the organic body both while the individual was alive and dead. This was called the *nbš*.

- ↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– No

Notes: The *nbš* appears to be more of a substitute for the body rather than something wholly different. The *nbš* is understood to eat, drink, participate in ritual practice, and perhaps even speak. Its primary unique aspect is that it has the potential to function in ritual/social contexts after the body's death.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Given the lack of corpses in mortuary contexts, some scholars speculate that the group may have practiced cremation. But there is no direct evidence for this practice.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– No

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Tombs dating to this period have not been discovered, even though mortuary artifacts and installations have been.

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Tombs dating to this period have not been discovered, even though mortuary artifacts and installations have been.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The royal family has a patron deity named Rakib-El, but it is unclear whether this deity was considered supreme by other denizens of the polity. He is completely absent from the Katumuwa Stele, for example, which seems to give pride of place to an instantiation of the storm-God Hadad.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: This is likely true given depictions of gods known from the site. Depictions of

Rakib-El in particular are assumed to exist, but no such depictions are indisputably of him.

- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Rakib-El means "rider god" and may be a reference to a storm-god riding on the clouds, an image known from the surrounding region.
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - Yes [specify]: He is the tutelary deity of the royal family.
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Righteousness seems to be defined in terms of sanction by Rakib-El and other members of the pantheon.
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: This deity is unique to this religious group and poorly attested.
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The tutelary deity can act by means of the king.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: In the Hadad Statue inscription (KAI 214), Panamuwa claims to have the favor of his god, but this section is somewhat damaged.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: The Hadad Statue inscription (KAI 214) threatens that violators of its prescriptions will not be looked upon favorably by Hadad. Presumably, Rakib-El could show the same displeasure.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Storm-god Hadad can eat and drink in mortuary rituals, but these are never described as needs or in terms of hunger and thirst.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In dreams:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In trance possession:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination practices:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: In contemporary inscriptions from Til Barsip (ca. 140 km from Zincirli), gods speak to humans by means of prophets, but no such specialists are known from Zincirli.

↳ Only through monarch
– Field doesn't know

Notes: In contemporary inscriptions from Hamath and Moab, gods speak directly to kings. At Zincirli, the gods communicate with the king, but direct speech is never recorded. It is also unclear whether or not the gods communicate exclusively with the king.

↳ Other form of communication with living:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:
– Yes

Notes: "Spirit" is not an attested concept in this culture, but some deceased persons remained present in social contexts.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:
– Yes

Notes: The culture did not distinguish between artistic representations of deceased persons and the persons themselves, so the deceased could be seen in the form of stone monuments. No evidence exists for their appearance in any other form.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
– Yes

Notes: The culture did not distinguish between artistic representations of deceased persons and the persons themselves, so the deceased could be theoretically be touched in the form of stone monuments. No evidence exists for their tangibility in any other form.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: The deceased pronounce blessings and curses on those who properly or improperly perform funerary rituals to them. However, those blessings and curses are actually carried out by deities.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The deceased pronounce blessings and curses on those who properly or improperly perform funerary rituals to them. However, those blessings and curses are actually carried out by deities.

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There appears to be no distinction between deceased persons before and after their deaths, but memory is never discussed.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Emotional responses of deceased persons are not discussed in primary sources.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Emotional responses of deceased persons are not discussed in primary sources.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Deceased persons can socially interact with the living through mortuary rituals, but direct communication is never discussed in primary sources.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Because the culture does not appear to distinguish artistic representations from

the figures represented, it may be possible that images of supernatural beings were understood as the beings themselves. This cannot currently be confirmed for Sam'al, however.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Because the culture does not appear to distinguish artistic representations from the figures represented, it may be possible that images of supernatural beings were understood as the beings themselves. This cannot currently be confirmed for Sam'al, however.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Because the culture does not appear to distinguish artistic representations from the figures represented, it may be possible that images of supernatural beings were understood as the beings themselves. This cannot currently be confirmed for Sam'al, however. That said, artistic representations of supernatural beings like sphinxes were used to indicate spatial boundaries between ritually important places. So if these representations were understood as the beings themselves, then they did have causal efficacy in how people moved through ritual space.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: These figures are never described in primary sources and are poorly understood.

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: Such beings are known elsewhere in ancient West Asia, but no such beings are known from Sam'al.

- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - Field doesn't know

 - ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

- ↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: Only the murder of cohabitants in Sam'al is explicitly forbidden.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: Only the murder of cohabitants in Sam'al is explicitly forbidden.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: No sexual taboos are recorded, but they exist in the surrounding polities.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: Supernatural beings clearly care about honoring ancestors, but there is no direct evidence for this respect being extended to living elders.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: The destruction of monuments can incur divine curses.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence that a concept of conversion existed for this group.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: Kulamuwa (KAI 24) claims to have brought about more economic fairness in the polity, and this is implied to be a sanctioned accomplishment from the perspective of the gods.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: Royal successors are explicitly enjoined to remember their predecessors, and failure to do so results in divine punishment.

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The gods are spoken of as defending the religious group from outside enemies.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Punishments include hunger and sleeplessness.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: One punishment is "terror."

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is a punishment in neighboring regions, so it may have been present in this group as well.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This punishment occurs in neighboring regions, but it is not directly attested here.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Some punishments are described very directly. Kulamuwa calls upon his gods to "smash the head" of anyone who destroys his monument.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Social norms are always prescribed alongside some appeal to a specific human and/or divine authority.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Certain sexual norms are assumed in neighboring cultures (such as Carchemish), but remain unattested for Sam'al.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

Notes: Livestock must be sacrificed in mortuary rituals.

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Certain rituals were prescribed with some regularity (e.g. seasonal or yearly repetition).

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Because the religious group is indistinguishable from the polity, members were occasionally required to go to war. It is unclear whether this had any religious component, however.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Based on an average crowd density of 2-3 people per square meter, the ceremonial theatre on the acropolis could accommodate crowds of around 10,000 up until it was bisected by King Bar-Rakib, after which its capacity may have been halved. This is significantly higher than an estimated population of 8,000. Assuming that 50% of that population may have been infirm or children, perhaps the entire “active population” of the polity could participate in some rituals. However, it is unclear how many people actually participated in large-scale rituals.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Ritual spaces were laid out with clear indicators of how to move through them, including texts that prescribed particular interpretations. However, it is unclear how people in antiquity actually interacted with these indicators.

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Ritual spaces were laid out with clear indicators of how to move through them, including texts that prescribed particular interpretations. However, it is unclear how people in antiquity actually interacted with these indicators.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Circumcision:

– No

↳ Food taboos:

– No

↳ Hair:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Artistic depictions of practitioners tend to rely upon standardized representations of hairstyles. The import of these is not clear, however.

↳ Dress:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Artistic depictions of practitioners reveal a standardized representation of certain forms of dress, but it is unclear whether these had any religious import.

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

Notes: Practitioners were known to wear or display amulets that were designed as miniaturizations of larger scale ritual monuments. For example, standardized mortuary ritual scenes are attested on both funerary monuments and on jewelry.

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The site does attest a unique written language (Sam'alian), but it is unknown whether it was perceived as archaic. Luwian also had a high impact on ritual language, but again the precise dimensions of this interaction are unknown.

↳ Other:

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Notes: The king could claim to be the father, mother, and brother of his subjects.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Notes: The same terminology is used at neighboring sites, so this was a broader cultural phenomenon.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Notes: Yādiya/Sam'al might also be described as a city-state with some control over the surrounding region. Current evidence suggests that power was highly centralized in the royal family and that non-royal elites derived power from association with the royal family.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Royal inscriptions claim that some royals provided social benefits to their citizens, but the precise nature of this support is currently unknown. There is still debate over the meaning of class categories in Sam'alian texts, and it is unknown how social benefits were proffered or even if the narrative served a purely ideological purpose.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: In the inscription on the Kulamuwa Orthostat, the king claims to have alleviated poverty for some of his citizens, but the inscription does not explain how he did so.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Iconographic depictions and inscriptions suggest that formal training for scribes and artisans was available, but it is currently unclear how this was provided and whether it was connected to the religious group.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Texts in Luwian found at the site may attest to formal education that was unconnected to the polity itself.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: For much of its history, the Sam'alians had formal interactions with the Assyrian Empire. The Nimrud wine lists provide evidence that Sam'alian emissaries traveled to the Assyrian capital to interact with Assyrian functionaries in state-sponsored rituals. It is possible that Assyrian officials also traveled to Sam'al.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Field doesn't know

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Sacrifices of livestock were required by some rituals on at least a yearly basis.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Because the religious group is not separated from other institutions, it may be possible that any political taxation would have been understood religiously. But no such taxation is attested.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Prescriptions exist for the legal resolution of criminal cases. These prescriptions were made by a particular king, but he required that they be carried out by the defendant's relatives. This passage is damaged, however, so this judicial procedure may have been more complicated.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: The only known punishment is stoning, which could presumably have resulted in death.

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: The only known punishment is stoning.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Once a vassal relationship to Assyria was established, group members may have been subject to some Assyrian legal prescriptions. No evidence of this remains, however.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: One inscription (that on the Hadad Statue of Panamuwa I) includes some prescriptions for ethical norms and judicial procedures, but it is unclear whether this reflects a formal code or a pronouncement unique to that king and his reign.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This may have been possible under Assyrian domination, but no evidence for such a case has been found.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:
– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Yes

Notes: This was true only during the period of vassalage to Assyria.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

- Yes

Notes: Sam'alian is unique to this site.

- ↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:
– Field doesn't know

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Yes

Notes: Inscriptions from the reign of Bar-Rakib, for example, demonstrate that he could use Sam'alian (the language specific to the group) as well as Official Aramaic (the lingua franca of the Assyrian Empire) and Hieroglyphic Luwian (a co-territorial language).

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Yes

Notes: Inscriptions from the reign of Bar-Rakib, for example, demonstrate that he could use Sam'alian (the language specific to the group) as well as Official Aramaic (the lingua franca of the Assyrian Empire) and Hieroglyphic Luwian (a co-territorial language).

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

- Field doesn't know

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: During the period of vassalage to Assyria, there is evidence for the import of foods from other regions in the empire.